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DESIGN STUDENTS' AWARENESS OF THEIR OWN DESIGN PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the topic of design students' perception of their own design processes. The relevance of the theme has to do mainly with the vital importance in the learning process of knowing how students become aware of their own learning and can reflect on their actions. In fact, this 'thinking about thinking', referred to as metacognition, can be used to help students 'learn how to learn.' In order to observe the degree of awareness Design students have about their own cognitive and design processes a research project was conducted among Portuguese students. Two methods were used: an electronic survey among Design students of the 5th grade of the Design Program in two sequential years (N=39 in total), and an experiment conducted with 32 students in the optional course 'Design process management' of a Master Design Program. The concatenated results of both methods are presented and discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Metacognition, design process, design process assessment

INTRODUCTION

Design education foreshadows the complexity of design problems. In order to become competent designers, students need to gain an understanding of how the various stages of design fit together into their total design process. They need to progress through the entire event and receive feedback on it. A complicated factor is that designing asks for the integration of many disciplines such as engineering, aesthetics, psychology, business, environmental issues, history, and so on. Furthermore, in design education another form of integration is also

important, that between the application of theoretical knowledge and the final physical embodiment of the design (Christiaans & Venselaar, 2005). Facing the kind of design problems as just mentioned students have to acquire expertise in not only having appropriate domain-specific knowledge, but also 'general process knowledge' (Anderson, 1987; Elio & Scharf, 1990, mentioned in Christiaans & Venselaar, 2005), referring to domain-independent knowledge of managing and monitoring the solution generating process, part of it being called metacognitive knowledge.

METACOGNITIVE KNOWLEDGE AND PROCESSES

Metacognitive knowledge is the knowledge or beliefs accumulated through experience and stored in long-term memory that concern the human mind and its doings. Some of this stored knowledge is declarative ('knowing that') and other procedural ('knowing how')(Chi, 1984). It involves decisions that help to identify the task on which one is currently working, to check on current progress of that work, to evaluate that progress, and to predict what the outcome of that progress will be. It has to do with the strategies used to improve cognitive performance by emphasizing knowledge about one's own mental states and operations (Flavell, 2000). According to Flavell (2000) metacognitive theory is not only about knowledge but also includes processes, meaning that it has to do with planning, monitoring, and regulating thoughts which is normally known as executive processes, that involve the interaction of two levels: a) the creative, associative, wandering mind, and b) the executive, trying to keep it on task. Paris and Winograd (1990, p.17) present metacognition as self-assessment that also refers to those two essential features: self-

appraisal and self-management of cognition. The first feature relates to people's personal reflections about both their own knowledge states and abilities, and their affective states concerning their knowledge, abilities, motivation, and characteristics as learners. The second feature refers to "metacognition in action", i.e. mental processes that help to "orchestrate aspects of problem solving" including "the plans that learners make before tackling a task", "the adjustments they make as they work", and "the revisions they make afterwards" (p.18). Important is to notice that as Butler & Winne state (1995, p.245) "theoreticians seem unanimous - the most effective learners are self-regulating" being accurate self-assessment of what is known or not known the key to effective self-regulation (Schoenfeld, 1987). Only when students know the state of their own knowledge they can effectively self-direct learning to the unknown. For a deeper understanding of the nature of metacognition it is interesting to consider Brown's work (1987) that distinguishes between knowledge about cognition and regulation of cognition. In her opinion knowledge about cognition can be "stable, stable but fallible or late developing" (p.67), meaning that information one has about his/her own cognitive processes usually remains relatively consistent. Regulation, on the other hand, can be "relatively unstable, rarely stable, and age independent" (p.68), i.e. the activities used to regulate and oversee learning are dynamic and variable. Furthermore, it is meaningful to mention how consciousness relates with metacognition knowledge and processes. For this purpose Koriat (2000) distinguishes two levels of experience, each with its own mode of operation: "The higher level involves an explicit mode of operation, characterized by relatively high degrees of consciousness and control, whereas the lower level involves an implicit mode of operation, characterized by relatively low degrees of consciousness and by automatic influences" (p.153). And as Koriat (2000) continuous "... it would seem natural to place metacognitive monitoring and control at the heart of the notion of consciousness" (p.151). Therefore, for her it is "surprising that some leading experts arrived at the conclusion that metacognitive processes are, in fact, more properly seen as being part of unconscious and implicit

functioning" (p.151). (see also Kelley & Jacoby, 1996; Reder & Schunn, 1996).

Assuming that an increase in mastering higher-order rules, as metacognition implies, improves problem solving, students have to learn to reflect on what they do whilst solving a design problem, and have to understand the processes and strategies underlying the most efficient way of reaching a design solution.

TWO STUDIES

In order to observe the degree of awareness design students have about their own cognitive and design processes a research project was conducted among Portuguese students. Two methods were used: an electronic survey among design students of the 5th grade of the Design Program and an experiment conducted in the optional course 'Design process management' of a Master Design Program in the same Portuguese university.

STUDY I: SURVEY

An electronic questionnaire was created to access the way students view design processes. In 2007 and 2009 it was spread among Master students in design. The number of students that answered the questionnaire was 45 (24 in 2007 and 21 in 2009), but only 39 questionnaires were valid. Due to space constraints we will only present in detail some of the most significant questions and answers.

One of the essential aspects to know about design processes is how the (student) designer starts after receiving the brief. Therefore a question was created (Q13) that asked the students "When facing a design problem for the first time what are your immediate concerns?"

Table 1. Immediate concerns when facing a design problem for the first time (from 1- less relevant concern, to 5 - most relevant concern)

Actions	Mean	sd
Draw/test ideas	3.51	1.21
Search existent solutions	3.97	0.93
Take the user's point of view	4.10	1.00
Evaluate the problem: its origins and limits	4.28	0.88
Search similar problems	3.41	0.82
Identify personal knowledge to be used in the design exercise	3.33	1.18

As Table 1 shows there is no single preferred start of the design problem. Students choose their own method, depending on either what they have learned or what they have consciously chosen as their favorite start.

Also relevant is to capture the phases students identify in their design process (Q14). That was done with an open question. The answers were categorized as presented in Table 2.

The conclusions are:

- a) A large majority of participants presume the existence of 3 phases that are defined either in a very general or in a detailed way. Those phases are the ‘Analysis or Research’ phase, the ‘Conceptual’ phase and the ‘Development of concept’ phase.
- b) A significant number of participants (46,2%) identify specifically what can be seen as a pre-phase of the conventional one (analysis) that has to do with the Brief acknowledgement.
- c) The initial phases are similar to the majority of the students, but the later in the design process the less information is given and if given at all, the descriptions become less and less homogeneous.

Table 2- Identified product design process phases

Moments in sequence	Synthetic Description	Count	%	%	4 Phases quest.
A	Acknowledge Brief/ Identification of problem and context of it	18	46,15%	46,15%	Initial / Conceptual
B	Research	25	64,10%	97,44%	
	Research of existent solutions	10	25,64%		
	Research of similar problems	3	7,69%		
C	Brainstorming	3	7,69%	7,69%	Development
D	Sketching/ concept generation *	33	84,62%	87,18%	
	Mental modelling of the ideas *	1	2,56%		
	Study of the users and their needs	2	5,13%		
	Planning the process	2	5,13%		
E	Evaluation and choice of a concept	11	28,21%	28,21%	Detailing
F	Experiment/ determine possible solutions*	5	12,82%	87%	
	Technical/ functional development*	29	74,36%		
	Ergonomic studies	1	2,56%		
	Correcting aspects of solutions	4	10,26%		
	Modeling 3D	4	10,26%		
G	Detailing	4	10,26%	10,26%	Pre-production
	Prototyping	6	15,38%	17,95%	
	Pre-engineering	1	2,56%		
H	Presentation	6	15,38%	15,38%	

Next, an attempt was made to isolate possible causes of differences in quality level regarding the design process outcome. Time and information management were two factors previously identified as having an impact on these design outcomes (Christiaans, 1992; Restrepo, 2004; Dorst, 1997).

Therefore, a question (Q16) was posed addressing specifically the time aspect: “Do you have difficulties in managing time along the design process?” An impressive amount of students (85%) stated to have difficulties indeed. Such an impressive percentage asked for a deeper exploration, as was done in a next question asking for the reasons behind that difficulty (Q17). See Figure 1 for the results. The reason most often mentioned is the “difficulty of predicting the necessary time to accomplish the different tasks” (19%). Second in the ranking of reasons is the subjects’ attribution of time management difficulties to “the amount of work they have to deliver in other disciplines” (11%). Closely following are three reasons: “Personal life”, “lack of organization and discipline” and “accumulation of work outside the Faculty”.

Figure 1 Reasons behind difficulties in design process' Time Management

Monitoring and planning your own process are typical metacognitive abilities. The answers on the question show that in spite of being aware of their poor time management students are still lacking these metacognitive capabilities.

Also important was to identify in which phases subjects usually spent more time (Q18) and what are the reasons behind it (Q19). The answers to those questions are presented in Table 3 and Figure 2 respectively.

Regarding the conceptual phase (that had the highest mean in terms of time spent) students elected as the main reasons for spending more time

in this phase: a) In this phase the decisions concern creativity which are harder to be taken (20%). b) This phase determines the whole process (20%). c) Having an innovative idea is crucial and difficult to generate (20%).

Table 3- Design Process phases that take more time

Phases of the Process	Mean	sd
Conceptual	4.00	1.03
Technical development	3.92	0.84
Detail phase	3.51	0.85
Pre-production	3.18	1.17

These results are consistent with scientific results from literature that identify the conceptual phase as a structural one. Rehman and Yan (2007) define it as a phase in which information processing and decision-making is very intensive as a consequence of the generation and evaluation of alternative ideas.

Figure 2 Reasons behind taking more time in Conceptual Phase

The authors also state that “the importance of conceptual design to the overall success of the product is crucial as once a final concept is chosen, the majority of the design decisions relating to the product behavior, cost and quality has been fixed as the subsequent product lifecycle activities (manufacturing, assembly, use and recycle/dispose) are implicitly determined by the concept. Moreover, detail design and manufacture cannot make up for a poor or inadequate conceptual design.” (p.170) Although time and information management were previously identified as being critical elements along the design process it was necessary to assess if that was the case with these students. Moreover, what are the other critical elements students identified (Q20)?

Particularly in this phase of the process reflection on one’s own actions and awareness of one’s own design process are crucial. A student will have a dialogue

with his/her teacher or with him/herself. Table 4 shows that next to domain knowledge about how and what is necessary in concept development, metacognition in terms of control over and monitoring the whole process including the consequences of one’s decisions in this phase for the coming phases is crucial according to the students.

Table 4- Critical elements along Design Process

Critical elements	Mean	sd
Understanding the brief	2.54	1.35
Obtaining market information	2.64	1.09
Obtaining technical information	3.38	0.96
Obtaining production information	3.38	0.78
Information management in general	2.85	1.04
Time(s) management of the process	3.51	1.28
Management of technical constraints	3.44	0.78
Interaction with the client	2.58	1.14
Execution of technical drawings/models	3.13	1.20
Execution of other drawings/models	2.82	1.17
Execution of the written parts of the project	2.62	1.18

STUDY II: EXPERIMENT

While the student’s perception about their own processes is central to this study, a design exercise was developed in the Design Processes Management course, an optional course offered to the students of the 5th grade of the Product Design and Graphic Design Under Graduation courses (the last year of the old curricula) of FA-TU Lisbon. This experiment aimed at getting information on how design students are being aware of their own processes. By this way a structured personal assessment about design processes could be acquired complementing the data gathered in the earlier survey study I. Besides this generic goal other objectives were:

- To test the consistency of the students perceptions gathered in the surveys;
- To enlarge the information about design process perception on the part of the students as their agents;
- To identify the elements students elect as being structural in design processes;
- To acquire knowledge of the perceived difficulties students have along their design process;
- To identify the degree of awareness students have about their own cognitive and design process.

The exercise/experiment ran during the first three classes of the course and was supported by a brief that was delivered to the 32 students (for a short version of the brief see Fig. 3). The brief stated that students had to describe their own design processes, defining the parameters of their analysis. Preferably the analysis should be presented as a diagram and

Individual Work

Title: Design Process - a systematic and critical reflection

Schedule: to be done during the 3 first weeks in one of the 2 hours classes of the course.

A - Work theme - the reflection upon design process made through the critical analysis of a personal example and by the proposal of the improvement of it

B - Methodology: the work is to be developed individually and during class's time. It must be constituted by two distinct elements: a retrospective analysis of a previous design process and the creation and proposal of a "new process". To do so the student must be deliver:

1. a **synthesis model of the studied process** - making explicit the different phases of it as well as aspects such the following: used information; constraints taken into account; decision made; swot analysis.
2. a **synthesis model of the "new process" that must be adequately detailed.**

C - Goals to reach/skills to explore: this is an exercise that as main goals:

1. the reflection upon the personal design processes of each student.
2. the development and consolidation of the analytical, interpretative and critical competences of the student.

D - Evaluation / Criteria
This exercise contributes in **30%** to the final mark of the course Design Processes Management.

a. Content evaluation criteria:

- i. Rigour and clarity on the model execution and its explanation;
- ii. Capability of clear expression of the reasoning lines that structure the analysis
- iii. Ability of correlating the different listed tasks
- iv. Ability of proposing and/or integrating other elements/ to perform other tasks that are justified to be necessary to the critical approach;
- v. Clear domain of the Portuguese language both in the written and spoken register.

b. Form aspects evaluation criteria

- i. Balance in aesthetical, colour, tactile and sound aspects from the part of the elements that form the whole;
- ii. Communication ability of the written graphic, tactile and sound elements;
- iii. Coherence of the relationship text and form;
- iv. Originality on the relationship between text and form;

Figure 3. Short version of the Brief delivered to the students

could be complemented by text. Moreover, they had to propose a way to improve their process modeling, again in a diagrammatic way. All participant students filled in an informed Consent. After the exercise there was a debrief session in order to collect their impressions about the exercise regarding: a) the difficulties they experienced; b) what they had learned from the exercise.

Diagrams as a tool to expose knowledge

It was expected that the diagrams created by students would be adequate to represent concepts and relations regarding quality, quantity, distribution, subdivision, modification and transformation (Massironi, 1982). The use of a

graphic image to model the phenomena is assumed to be an adequate research instrument as well as a good vehicle to scientific information. What we get from the diagrams of the design processes of each student is their understanding of a design process in its components, relationship among elements, level of dependence between elements, dominance and subjugation of elements, and emphasis and exclusion of elements.

Main results of the experiment

The large majority of the students had obvious difficulties to deliver the required outcomes.

According to them it had to do with the fact that they were not used neither to analyze their own processes nor to describe them. Furthermore, the expressed preference of presenting the processes in a diagrammatic way was for them an additional difficulty. They asked for an example of what was expected for them to deliver, but they didn't get one. Only 29 students finished the exercise and it is on the basis of their work that the results are presented.

Three approaches were observed among the students:

- A more conservative one, both in formal/ communicational aspects and in content structuring, where students ruled their own model construction according to the familiar phases of the design process, and listed the tasks to be developed, time spent, tools used, positive and negative points of each phase. This approach had the preference of the student majority (69%). Some of the diagrams were complemented with a descriptive text that contained more details about the issues addressed in it. The reasons to support such option were questioned in the debrief moment. In this debrief the majority of the students confirmed to have had a hard time to describe their own processes. They got fixated in the process phases determined by the brief of the exercise they were analyzing. Besides, it was hard for them to identify what could be the determinant parameters in design processes and their role in it. An example of this type of diagram can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of conservative diagram - student Rita Henriques

- A more creative approach (in graphic and content aspects) where students, although recognizing the different phases of the design process in a way they are used to in the design studio, made their analysis according to parameters they had found to be essential in design processes. In this case 21% of the students presented their own processes with the inclusion of non-literally demanded elements such as: new parameters of analysis or graphic elements that communicated different dimensions of the process. Also important in this type of exercises is the use of graphic elements to describe almost in 'visual' ways some key issues of the process. An example of this type of approach can be seen in Figures 5 and 6.
- An approach close to a 'story telling' report, very literary and supported by the images and other elements of the design process under analysis. The percentage of subjects that adopted this approach was the lowest (10%).

Figure 5. Example of a creative diagram - student Mariana Coutinho's design process

The synthesis of the analysis of the outcomes on this exercise was made through the use of two inductive

Figure 6. Example of a creative diagram - student David Francisco's design process

content analysis grids one of which is presented as Table 5. Data categorization occurred taking into account the results obtained in the survey as well as the literary critics done in this research.

The two inductive grids aim at presenting data in a concise and rigorous way trying to reduce the enormous amount of information into categories/patterns of solutions developed by the students. The first grid offers the summary of the exercise in its structural elements: phases, descriptors used; identified problems; listed methods; proposed reformulations with a general analysis of the outcomes in terms of the model created (its characteristics) and of the written information delivered.

The second grid (Table 5) presents the three approaches as a result of the critical and deeper analysis of the information presented in the first grid. Both grids show that the factors that were identified by the students as being more critical along the design process were again information management and time management (similar to what was observed in the survey). However, this exercise also revealed that there are other key factors that students find determinant in the design process: the decision making process is one of these. Also relevant to mention is that the possibility of representing graphically their own design process gave some students the possibility of expressing in more creative ways the richness and the complexity of those processes.

Apparently, and according to students in their debrief moment, this way of presenting their evaluation of the process worked for them as a facilitator in reflecting upon both an existent design process and upon design processes in general.

Regarding the two analyses that had to be made (a critical assessment of an existent design process and a proposal for an improved design process), the majority of the students found it very hard to propose an alternative/improved model. Those who made such a new model did it on the basis of proposing improvements of the negative aspects enclosed in the design process they had to analyze.

CONCLUSIONS

Two methods were used to make explicit the perception students have of their own design process disclosing the knowledge they have of it and how they regulate their learning process. The conclusions to be made are twofold:

1. On metacognitive knowledge and processes (inferred on the basis of this study);
2. On specific knowledge and metacognitive action about product design processes.

CONCLUSIONS REGARDING METACOGNITIVE KNOWLEDGE AND PROCESSES

One first conclusion that can be taken is that addressing the way students perceive their design practice creates a growing awareness about their learning process. That can be seen, for example, by the difficulties they have of describing their processes without following the given structure they received from the design studio teacher. But when they take the more creative analysis of their process they do it because they go beyond the formal phases and they question what is meant to be learned and to be achieved in the whole process.

A second conclusion is that the use of the two methods is complementary, i.e. the exercise with diagrams is richer in terms of the outcomes. In fact, with the survey we captured a mix of socially desirable answers with a 'first reflection' on knowledge acquisition, process characteristics and constraints. With the exercise in its three approaches (conservative, creative and story telling) we got a more mature and deeper reflection on those issues.

Table 5. Experiment analysis: Main characteristics of the three types of outcomes

		CONVENTIONAL DIAGRAMS (20)		CREATIVE DIAGRAMS (6)		DESCRIPTIVE (REPORTS) (3)	
		Analysis of the design process (based on previous design)	Proposed design process	Analysis of the design process (based on previous design)	Proposed design process	Analysis of the design process (based on previous design)	Proposed design process
CONTENT	structure	Dependent on design brief specifications of phases	structured upon the design phases student uses	not necessarily dependent on the design phases of the brief; more flexible structure	it can take a high level of abstraction	extensive description of the process sometimes close to a diary language	descriptive methodology or just a descriptive text that advances ways of improving the experienced negative aspects of the process
	parameters/descriptions	most often used; design phases; task definitions; chronogram; methods; negative/positive aspects	identical parameters making use of the negative aspects to find out solutions to overcome failure	social interaction; stimuli; cognitive aspects; decision analysis; constraint analysis; facilitators	identical to the analysis of the existing design process	hard to isolate in this 'story telling' process	conventional: in the cases a methodology is presented where the parameters are addressed in the conventional mode
	level of abstraction from the design	low - the analysis is made based on the constraints and context of the design process under study	low to medium - some proposals are still dependent on the particular problems found out in the design process that was analyzed	medium to high - analysis is based on a process but broad categories are created and inductive thinking occurs	medium to high - normally higher than in the analysis of a 'real situation' the levels of abstraction are superior	complete dependence on the images of the design done	variable - can be dependent or completely independent through the proposal of an existing methodology
	more relevant aspects	Regarding content the most relevant aspects are: 1. conventional diagrams convey in a literal way the design process being studied. That apparently constrained the possibility of induction in order to create a more critical assessment of the process. 2. This representation made it possible for the students to get aware of their own process, although it was hard for them to isolate the categories upon which the analysis would be done. 3. The creative approach was done in two ways: content and form. Regarding content the creativity occurred by the creation of parameters of analysis that were not conventional or found in the existing methodologies. 4. In general, the task of describing an existing process was more successful than to propose a new one. That was done either by proposing the improvement of negative aspects previously pointed out or in vague terms, supported by existing design methodologies.					
FORM	representation	sequential scheme; notation of boxes; geometric forms connected through the use of lines, arrows; a color code is normally used to enhance communication and help to isolate and/or group some of the elements	similar to the representation in the case of the analysis of a previous design	intensive use of fluid forms; of analogies translating several aspects of the design process	normally it is a natural sequence of what was developed in the analysis of a previous design	the common use of images done in reports; images complementing the information given in text	written text only
	use of images	low - sometimes there is the use of some images to put in context the 'reading' of the diagram	non existent	non existent	non existent	extensive use of images that illustrate the descriptive text	non existent
	more relevant aspects	1. The visual representation of the design process in general benefited the communication of those processes. 2. Even in conventional representations it was possible to convey expressively the relationship among parts and the dynamics of the process itself. 3. The creative representations that explored more the form aspects gave some students the possibility of going deeper in the analysis. 4. It was also visible that the students that had a more creative approach were the ones that had more ability to engage in inductive thought.					

CONCLUSIONS REGARDING KNOWLEDGE AND METACOGNITIVE ACTION ON PRODUCT DESIGN PROCESSES

The survey and the design exercise proposing a visual representation of the design process were two methods used to access information about the same

subject: determinants of the design process in the view of design students.

The results on the survey showed that information management and time management were critical elements of the design process. That is analogous to studies in the fields of design cognition and design

methodology done by several authors (Cross, 2006; Restrepo, 2004; Dorst, 1997; Christiaans, 1992). Also relevant is the fact that most of the students describe design process phases in similar ways being more detailed (in terms of the tasks to be developed) in the initial phases and less in the last ones: detailing and pre-production. Another result of this survey concerns the use of methods/tools to help manage the process. It was found that students mainly make (use of) checklists that have no effective influence in time and information management. A further conclusion is that the conceptual phase is the one students get more concentrated on and the one richest in terms of 'events' i.e. blockage, information management, and contact with external persons such as peers and teachers. Finally it was possible to observe some other fundamental issues such as the design strategy used by students - problem, solution or co-evolution driven (Christiaans & Restrepo, 2001; Almendra, 2010).

The main results of the experiment show that students have low conscience of their own design processes. However, the use of its diagrammatic description helps them to acknowledge several aspects of the process they never reflected upon before. Moreover, the outcomes show that the majority of the students had difficulties with inductive thinking. Starting from the description and analysis of a specific design problem to ending up with a proposal of a general model to frame the design process was hard to accomplish. A conclusion might be that the use of diagrams or any other visual schematic representation can facilitate the delivery of information about the design process. That is because graphic representations, seen as a way of analyzing an 'object', could more easily be adopted by these 'visual experts' as a rich means to proceed to the process decomposition in its structural elements and in the multiple and diverse relationship that are established among them. In the end it was the students concluded that the exercise helped them to acknowledge in a more explicit and in-depth way their own design process. Because diagrams ask for a student's ability to create synthetic and organized information the outcome of this method has more impact on the student than filling in a

questionnaire in which the student's intervention is lower.

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